

The Influence of Audio Visual (Video) Imagination on Hospitalization Stress in Hemodialysis Patients at the Siti Khadijah Islamic Hospital, Palembang

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Audio visual, Imagination, Stress

Received : 20, August

Revised : 15, September

Accepted: 9, October

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ABSTRACT

Kupriyanov and Zhdanov (2014) stated that current stress is an attribute of modern life. The aim of this research is to determine the effect of imagination using audio-visual (video) on hospitalization stress in hemodialysis patients at the Siti Khadijah Islamic Hospital, Palembang. The research design used was pre-experiment with a one group pre-post test design approach. The sample consisted of 20 people. Sampling was carried out using accidental sampling technique. Then the data was analyzed using the nonparametric Marginal Homogeneity test. The results of data analysis using the non-parametric Marginal Homogeneity test showed that there was a significant effect of providing audio-visual (video) imagination therapy before and after on stress in hemodialysis patients with a p value of $0.001 < \alpha (0.05)$.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (2017) reports that patients suffering from chronic kidney failure have increased by 50% from the previous year, globally the incidence of chronic kidney failure is more than 500 million people and those who have to live dependent on dialysis (hemodialysis) is 1.5 million people. Chronic kidney failure is among the 12 common causes of death in the world, accounting for 1.1 million deaths due to chronic kidney failure which has increased by 31.7% from 2010 to 2015 (Neuen in Sri Atun W, 2020). Based on the Prevalence of Basic Health Research (Riskesmas) in 2018, the prevalence of chronic kidney failure based on doctor's diagnosis in the population aged > 15 years, the number of chronic kidney failure sufferers in Indonesia is 0.38% or 713,783 cases of the total population of Indonesia. Meanwhile, the number of chronic kidney failure sufferers in South Sumatra is 0.27% or 22,013 cases, while CKD patients who are actively undergoing hemodialysis in South Sumatra are estimated to reach 17.79% (RI Ministry of Health, 2018).

Chronic Kidney Failure (CKD) is a global health problem experienced in society where it has very high prevalence and mortality. Chronic Kidney Failure is usually characterized by a decrease in kidney function and even loss of kidney function for a long time (Nurchayati, et al, 2019). Chronic kidney failure (CKD) is a progressive disorder of kidney function, where the body is unable to maintain metabolism, fails to maintain fluid and electrolyte balance, which results in an increase in urea. Chronic kidney failure patients have the characteristics of being persistent, incurable and requiring treatment in the form of hemodialysis, peritoneal dialysis, kidney transplantation and long-term outpatient care (Black & Hawks, 2018). Dialysis Procedure Dialysis is a procedure performed to remove fluids, waste and toxins that have accumulated in the body. This process should be carried out naturally by the kidneys. However, when the kidneys cannot carry out their function, a dialysis procedure is needed. So far, there are 2 types of dialysis that are commonly performed, namely: Hemodialysis, which is a procedure carried out using tools to clean the blood. Peritoneal dialysis, which is a procedure performed using the abdominal peritoneal membrane to filter dirty blood (Emma, 2018).

Stress is the body's reaction to changes that require physical, psychological and emotional response, regulation and/or adaptation. Stress can originate from situations, conditions, thoughts, and/or cause frustration, anger, nervousness, and stress. The stress level is divided into 3: Light, Medium, Heavy. (Silverman, et 2020)

The occurrence of stress due to stressors that are felt and perceived by the individual is a threat that can cause stress. CKD patients undergo Hemodialysis therapy 1-2 times every week and spending several hours will make them experience tension, stress, stress and depression which is different for each individual which has a negative impact on their quality of life and health (Saputra, 2020). Stress in CKD patients can also be triggered by having to undergo HD for life, not to mention having to face complications from CKD itself such as disorders of the heart and blood vessel system, anemia, hypertension, fertility problems for both men and women, Hospitalization is a process, where for some reason, whether an emergency or disaster, requires

staying in the hospital undergoing therapy and treatment until being returned home. Therefore, researchers took a problem formulation: Is there an effect of imagination using audio-visual (video) media on hospitalization stress in hemodialysis patients at Siti Khadijah Islamic Hospital, Palembang? General Objective: To determine the influence of imagination using audio-visual (video) on hospitalization stress in hemodialysis patients at Siti Khadijah Islamic Hospital Palembang. Specific Objective: To determine the level of stress in hospitalization in hemodialysis patients before being given imagination using audio visual (video) at the Siti Khadijah Islamic Hospital in Palembang, the level of hospitalization stress in Palembang was known. After being given imagination using audio-visual (video) at the Siti Khadijah Hospital in Palembang, the effects of hospitalization stress were known before and after being given imagination using audio visual (video) at Siti Khadijah Hospital, Palembang.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Hospitalization is a process which, for planned and emergency reasons, requires the child to stay in hospital, undergo therapy and treatment until he is returned home (Supartini, 2004). When being treated in hospital, children have to face a strange environment, unfamiliar care providers, be it medical or nursing. Often they have to undergo procedures that involve pain, loss of independence and various things they don't know (MurtutikL and Wahyuni, 2013). The physical environment of the hospital such as buildings or treatment rooms, equipment, distinctive smells, the white clothes of hospital staff and the social environment such as fellow child patients and the attitude of health workers themselves, so that the feelings that are often experienced by children are feelings of anxiety, tension, painful.

Some popular psychological terms are often confused with "stress". In essence, of course, this word refers to a condition of a person who experiences excessive emotional and/or time demands that make it difficult to function effectively in all areas of life. This condition can result in the emergence of quite a number of symptoms, such as depression, chronic fatigue, irritability, anxiety, impotence, and quality of life. low work (Richards, 2010). Stress is a common problem that occurs in human life. Kupriyanov and Zhdanov (2014) stated that current stress is an attribute of modern life. This is because stress has become an inevitable part of life. Whether in school, work, family, or anywhere else, stress can be experienced by anyone. Stress can also happen to anyone, including children, teenagers, adults or the elderly. In other words, stress definitely happens to anyone and anywhere. The problem is that if a person experiences a lot of stress, the impact is to endanger his physical and mental condition. This was confirmed by Lin and Huang (2014) who stated that stress that is physically and mentally harmful can be experienced by everyone. Stress is a group of physiological changes resulting from the body being exposed to dangerous threats. Stress has two components: physical, namely physiological changes, and psychological, namely how a person feels about the situation in his life.

These changes in physical and psychological states are called stressors (experiences that induce a stress response) (Pinel, 2009) or who are elderly. In other words, stress definitely happens to anyone and anywhere. The problem is that if a person experiences a lot of stress, the impact is to endanger his physical and mental condition. This was confirmed by Lin and Huang (2014) who stated that stress that is physically and mentally harmful can be experienced by everyone. Stress is a group of physiological changes resulting from the body being exposed to dangerous threats. Stress has two components: physical, namely physiological changes, and psychological, namely how a person feels about the situation in his life. These changes in physical and psychological states are called stressors (experiences that induce a stress response) (Pinel, 2009) or who are elderly. In other words, stress definitely happens to anyone and anywhere. The problem is that if a person experiences a lot of stress, the impact is to endanger his physical and mental condition. This was confirmed by Lin and Huang (2014) who stated that stress that is physically and mentally harmful can be experienced by everyone. Stress is a group of physiological changes resulting from the body being exposed to dangerous threats. Stress has two components: physical, namely physiological changes, and psychological, namely how a person feels about the situation in his life. These changes in physical and psychological states are called stressors (experiences that induce a stress response) (Pinel, 2009) The problem is that if a person experiences a lot of stress, the impact is to endanger his physical and mental condition. This was confirmed by Lin and Huang (2014) who stated that stress that is physically and mentally harmful can be experienced by everyone. Stress is a group of physiological changes resulting from the body being exposed to dangerous threats. Stress has two components: physical, namely physiological changes, and psychological, namely how a person feels about the situation in his life. These changes in physical and psychological states are called stressors (experiences that induce a stress response) (Pinel, 2009) The problem is that if a person experiences a lot of stress, the impact is to endanger his physical and mental condition. This was confirmed by Lin and Huang (2014) who stated that stress that is physically and mentally harmful can be experienced by everyone. Stress is a group of physiological changes resulting from the body being exposed to dangerous threats. Stress has two components: physical, namely physiological changes, and psychological, namely how a person feels about the situation in his life. These changes in physical and psychological states are called stressors (experiences that induce a stress response) (Pinel, 2009) This was confirmed by Lin and Huang (2014) who stated that stress that is physically and mentally harmful can be experienced by everyone. Stress is a group of physiological changes resulting from the body being exposed to dangerous threats. Stress has two components: physical, namely physiological changes, and psychological, namely how a person feels about the situation in his life. These changes in physical and psychological states are called stressors (experiences that induce a stress response) (Pinel, 2009) This was confirmed by Lin and Huang (2014) who stated that stress that is physically and mentally harmful can be experienced by everyone. Stress is a group of physiological

changes resulting from the body being exposed to dangerous threats. Stress has two components: physical, namely physiological changes, and psychological, namely how a person feels about the situation in his life. These changes in physical and psychological states are called stressors (experiences that induce a stress response) (Pinel, 2009).

Understanding Imagination and Imagination Guidance

According to Rachmawati and Kurniaty (2010: 54), imagination is a person's ability to think divergently which is carried out without limits, as widely as possible and with multiple perspectives in response to stimulation. This ability is very useful for developing children's creativity. With imagination, children can develop their thinking and creative powers, without being limited by reality and everyday reality. He is free to think according to his experiences and fantasies. Imagination will help children's ability to think, flexibility and originality. Imagination for young children is very important, because at that age there is a sensitive period, where children have potential that needs to be developed. According to Yulianti (2010: 10), kindergarten age makes children sensitive to receiving various efforts to develop all their potential. At that time, physical and psychological functions mature, ready to respond to stimulation provided by the environment, so that they can be used to develop physical abilities, cognition, language, social emotional, self-concept, discipline, independence, art, morals and religious values.

Benefits of Imagination Guidance

Imagination guidance has been established as a standard form of therapy to be effective in reducing anxiety, and providing a relaxing effect on adults and children, can reduce pain, invasive actions that cause pain, insomnia, prevent allergic reactions, and can also lower blood pressure. (Synder & Lindquist, 2006). Jrank (2011) stated that imagination guidance has been proven effective in helping individuals learn to: 1) relax/relax, 2) change or control negative emotions due to a certain situation (for example: being sick in hospital), 3) preparing individuals to face the future (such as: what do you want to be when you grow up), 4) eliminating or changing desired behavior (such as: unhealthy lifestyle), 5) increasing the effectiveness of pain management,

Imagination guidance can channel skill achievement, overcome anxiety in normal life including improving motor skills, being calm in facing or following objectives, giving speeches/presentations in front of many people. Currently, visualization imagination guidance has been modified and applied in the fields of business, industry, education, medicine and nursing as well as in families for raising children (Jrank, 2011). Imagination techniques have now been combined with various nursing and treatment measures through psychotherapy approaches, behavioral and cognitive procedures, behavior modification, cognitive processing therapy, multimodal therapy, rational emotional therapy and hypnotherapy (Jrank, 2011). The combination of these imagination techniques aims for general use in: 1) helps individuals to prepare themselves about things they fear in the future, 2) as a pleasant relaxation method, 3)

eliminates and reduces unwanted behavior using unpleasant images, 4) explores unpleasant feelings with imagination techniques, 5) can using images to obtain goals and manage situations, 6) using imagination to overcome feared things (Jrank, 2011). Audio Visual Imagination Technique (Video) 5) can use images to achieve goals and manage situations, 6) use imagination to overcome feared things (Jrank, 2011). Audio Visual Imagination Technique (Video) 5) can use images to achieve goals and manage situations, 6) use imagination to overcome feared things (Jrank, 2011). Audio Visual Imagination Technique (Video) Imagination guidance is a therapy to reduce stress by providing a relaxing effect on patients. This is combined with using video media which is popular with children and is appropriate to the type of media for school age children so that it can foster their abilities, creativity and imagination (Palmer, 2013). When experiencing stress due to hospitalization, what can be done is stress management such as relaxation (imagination guidance) to reduce negative responses in children. This imagination guidance uses a person's imagination, which is the language used by the brain to communicate with the body. The imagination is then processed by the brain to the thalamus sensor through images formed from stimuli received by the senses such as images, aromas, tastes, sounds and touch. When there is stimulation in the form of images of things you like, the stored memory will reappear and give rise to a perception of the actual sensation experience, so that a behavioral response pattern is formed that is in accordance with the meaning of the stimulus received.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

METHODOLOGY

The research design used in this research is pre-experiment with a one group pre-post test design approach. In this design, before being given treatment, the sample is first given a pre-test (initial test) and at the end of the imagination is given a post-test (final test). This design was used in accordance with the objectives to be achieved, namely wanting to know the effect of audio-visual (video) imagination on hospitalization stress in haemodialysis patients. The following is a pre-experimental research design table with a one group pre-post test design approach.

<i>Pretest</i>	<i>Treatment</i>	<i>Posttest</i>
O ₁	X	O ₂

Figure 2. Methodology

The samples used in the research were all haemodialysis patients undergoing hospitalization at RSI Siti Khadijah Palembang. The sample was taken using non-probability sampling using an accidental sampling technique, namely by taking cases or respondents who happened to be present or available in a place according to the research context (Notoatmodjo, 2012). In this study, researchers used a maximum experimental sample size of 20 samples based on the Roscoe, 1982 formula quoted in Sugiyono (2016). Inclusion Criteria include Haemodialysis patient under going hospitalization in hospital, Haemodialysis patient both men and women who under go treatment at least 1 x 24 hours, Haemodialysis patient who can communicate well, hemodialysis patient willing to be a respondent. Exclusion criteria include hemodialysis patients who dropped out of the hospital.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Analysis carried out on each variable from the research results. In general, this analysis only produces frequency and percentage distributions for each variable (Notoatmojo, 2007).

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Hospitalization Stress in hemodialysis patients Before being given Audio Visual (Video) Imagination at Home Siti Khadijah Islamic Hospital Palembang

No	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
1	Light	17	85.0
2	Currently	3	15.0
Total		20	100

Based on Table 2 above, it shows the stress of hospitalization in hemodialysis patients Before conducting audio visual imagination, mild stress was higher for 17 respondents (85.0%) compared to moderate stress for 3 people (15.0%).

Table 3. Frequency Distribution of Hospitalization Stress in hemodialysis patients After being given Audio Visual (Video) Imagination at Home Siti Khadijah Islamic Hospital Palembang

No	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
1	Normal	14	70.0
2	Mild stress	5	25.0
3	Moderate stress	1	5.0
Total		20	100

Based on Table 3 above, it shows that hospitalization stress on hemodialysis patients After conducting audio visual (video) imagination, 14 respondents (70%) showed that normal stress was higher than 5 respondents (25%) for mild stress and 1 respondent for moderate stress (5%).

Bivariate analysis

This will be seen statistically on the differences in hospitalization stress in hemodialysis patients before and after being given audio-visual imagination (video). Before bivariate analysis was carried out, researchers no longer tested data distribution with a normality test because the measurement results were already categorized, the measurement results used were more than two categories, so the nonparametric test used was the Marginal Homogeneity Test, resulting in a p value <0.05 .

Table 4. Effect of Hospitalization Stress on hemodialysis patients Before and After Being Given Audio Visual Imagination (video) at RSI Siti Khadijah Palembang

Amount category Stress	After			Total	P value
	normal	Mild stress	Moderate stress		
Before					
Mild stress	11	5	1	17	0.001
Very heavy	3	0	0	3	
Total	14	5	1	20	

Based on the table above, it can be seen that hospitalization stress on hemodialysis patients there was mild stress before the audio-visual (video) imagination was carried out and it became normal after the audio-visual (video) imagination was carried out, there were 11 respondents, those in the category of mild stress before the audio-visual (video) imagination and those in the mild stress category after the audio-visual (video) imagination.) was 5 respondents, then the mild stress category before the audio-visual (video) imagination was carried out and the moderate stress category after the audio-visual (video) imagination was carried out was 1. The results of the non-parametric statistical test (Marginal Homogeneity Test) obtained a value of ρ value = 0.001 < 0.05, which means there is a difference in hospitalization stress on hemodialysis patients before and after audio visual (video) imagination is carried out so that the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected.

DISCUSSION

Stress of hospitalization of hemodialysis patients before being given audio visual (video) imagination

Based on research results which is done in RSI Siti Khadijah Palembang was obtained from 20 respondents stress level of hemodialysis patients Before being given audio visual (video) imagination, there were 17 people (85%) in the mild stress category, more than the stress level in the moderate stress category, namely 3 people (15%).

Hospitalization is a process where for certain reasons or an emergency requires a child to stay in hospital, undergo treatment therapy until he is returned home (Supartini, 2004). Hospitalization is one of the causes of stress both in the family (Nursalam, et al, 2008). The results of measuring stress levels in theory state that stress is divided into 5 categories, namely normal, mild stress, moderate stress, severe stress, and very severe stress/panic (Lovibond & Lovibond, 2003), while the research results obtained only have 2 categories, namely mild stress and moderate stress.

Hospitalization stress of hemodialysis patients after being given audio-visual (video) imagination

Based on the results of research conducted at RSI Siti Khadijah Palembang, it was found that from 20 respondents the stress level of hemodialysis patients after being given audio-visual (video) imagination in the normal category was 14 people (70%), higher than the stress level in the mild stress category, namely 5 people (25%) and the moderate stress category was 1 person (5%). imagination has been established as a standard form of therapy to be effective in reducing anxiety, and providing a relaxing effect on adults and children, can reduce pain, invasive actions that cause pain, insomnia, prevent allergic reactions, and can also lower blood pressure (Synder & Lindquist, 2006).

Jrank (2011) states that imagination has been proven to be effective in helping individuals learn to: 1) relax/relax, 2) change or control negative emotions due to a certain situation (for example: being sick in hospital), 3) preparing individuals to face the future (such as: what do you want to become when you grow up), 4) eliminating or changing desired behavior (such as: unhealthy lifestyle), 5) increasing the effectiveness of pain management, 6) being able to face difficult situations, 7) modifying new and enjoyable learning, 8) become more motivated in facing a problem, 9) control anger, 10) manipulate stress and anxiety positively.

The Effect of Hospitalization Stress on Hemodialysis Patients Before and After Being Given Audio Visual (Video) Imagination at RSI Siti Khadijah Palembang

Based on the results of the non-parametric marginal homogeneity test, it can be concluded that there is an influence between stress before and after being given audio-visual imagination (video) hemodialysis patients with p value = 0.001 < 0.05. imagination has been established as a standard form of therapy to be effective in reducing anxiety, and providing a relaxing effect on adults and children, can reduce pain, invasive actions that cause pain, insomnia, prevent allergic reactions, and can also lower blood pressure (Synder & Lindquist, 2006). The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Masulili (2013) who stated There is a difference There was a significant mean hospitalization stress score before and after the imagination intervention with (p v = 0.004).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of research on 20 respondents, it was found that the hospitalization stress of hemodialysis patients before being given audio visual imagination was 20 people with a percentage of mild stress of 17 people (85%) and moderate stress of 3 people (15%), Stress of hospitalization of hemodialysis patients after being given audio imagination. 20 people with a normal percentage of 14 people (70%), 5 people with mild stress (25%), and 1 person with moderate stress (5%), There is a difference in the stress of hospitalization of hemodialysis patients before and after being given audio-visual imagination with p value = 0.001 < 0.05.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

It is hoped that the results of this research can be used as comparison material for conducting further research regarding audio-visual (Video) imagination interventions which can reduce stress levels in adults with chronic illnesses and children due to hospitalization.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Thank you to all parties who have been involved in this research and hopefully it will become the latest knowledge and can be added to research variables, especially in other chronic diseases.

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